

Jex

High Performance Computing at the MRC Laboratory of Medical Sciences

George Young
MRC LMS, London, UK
george.young@lms.mrc.ac.uk

Adil Coktas
MRC LMS, London, UK
adil.coktas@lms.mrc.ac.uk

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Introduction

Jex is a Tier-3 high performance computing (HPC) cluster installed at the MRC Laboratory of Medical Sciences (LMS). Jointly managed by the LMS IT and Bioinformatics Facilities, Jex was established in 2023 to cement the Institute's ongoing support for computational biology.

Built with scalability in mind, Jex is designed to accommodate evolving computational requirements and will continue to be enhanced with further hardware and software features, with a focus on on-demand interactive applications.

Jex

The cluster is named in honour of Sophia Jex-Blake, a leading campaigner for the right of women to study and practise medicine in the UK. Jex-Blake was the third woman registered as a doctor with the UK General Medical Council and the first practising female doctor in Scotland. She later helped establish two all-female medical schools and, with those she trained, dedicated 16 years to providing affordable care to poor women in Edinburgh, retiring in 1889.

User Base

In addition to its status as an MRC Institute, the LMS forms the larger part of the Institute of Clinical Sciences (ICS), one of eight Schools, Institutes, and Departments comprising the Faculty of Medicine at Imperial College London.

All LMS and ICS staff can request access to the provision. Divided between more than 30 research groups, Jex is available to over 400 research staff and post-graduate students.

Intended Application

The LMS is an interdisciplinary research environment in which scientists and clinicians collaborate to advance the understanding of biology and its application to medicine. Research within the Institute focusses on the genetic, epigenetic, and physiological bases of health and disease, including through the integration of cutting-edge imaging.

Jex is designed and maintained to this end, with software lists specific to these needs and with scheduling systems designed to support a range of job types.

System Description

Jex is a SuperMicro cluster running Rocky 8 Linux. It is composed of nodes sharing the Intel Ice Lake architecture.

Dedicated head nodes virtualise high-availability login and cluster management systems alongside storage nodes provisioning cluster-local storage and ephemeral scratch space. Batch processing nodes, separated into CPU, GPU, and high memory (HMEM) groups, provide 586 TFLOPs (FP32, single-precision performance) in the initial installation.

Job Management

The SLURM (Yoo, Jette, and Grondona 2003) queuing system is deployed to efficiently route jobs of varying resource requirements to separate partitions and quality of service (QoS) groups. Research groups are assigned individual QoS groups to proactively maintain fair-share.

Jex maintains dedicated high-priority partitions for interactive jobs and, separately, for workflow management controller processes, including Nextflow (Di Tommaso et al. 2017) and snakemake (Mölder et al. 2021). To encourage use of these partitions and to ensure quality of service, processes running on the virtualised login service are limited by Linux cgroups policies and are monitored by Arbiter2 (Gardner, Migacz, and Haymore 2019), which notifies and penalises users with aberrant activity profiles.

Software

Jex utilises the Spack (Gamblin et al. 2015) package management system to build and maintain its scientific software stack. Over 150 applications are currently available, in addition to a range of containerised and pre-built softwares.

Curated databases and communal resources exposed to the end-user are maintained on cluster-local storage for use with the deployed applications.

Further Information

Available to LMS staff, up to date information on Jex, training resources, and guides can be accessed via the HPC wiki.

Information regarding the MRC LMS and on the Institute’s IT and Bioinformatics Facilities can be found via the website: lms.mrc.ac.uk.

Keywords HPC, High Performance Computing, Cluster Computing, Linux

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